

GUIDEBOOK TO
THE NATURAL REGIONS OF KANSAS

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Friends University
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Soils

General Soil Map Association Series From soil map

Glossary From soil handbook

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Mushrooms List

Ferns List

Common Grasses List

Common Forbs List
 Woody Plants & Vines List
 Invertebrate Animals
 Gastropods List
 Unionid Mussels Matrix: species vs river systems
 Aquatic Insect Larvae List
 Dragonflies & Damselflies List
 Butterflies List
 Vertebrate Animals
 Lampreys & Relatives Matrix: species vs river systems
 Ray-finned Fishes Matrix: species vs river systems
 Amphibians Matrix: species vs Natural Regions
 Mammals Matrix: species vs Natural Regions
 Turtles Matrix: species vs Natural Regions
 Reptiles Matrix: species vs Natural Regions
 Birds Matrix: species vs Natural Regions
 Fossils Matrix: species vs Natural Regions
 Archaeological Sites Matrix: site location vs Natural Regions
 References Cited To be added
 Other References To be added
 Kansas Natural History Inventory

THE NATURAL REGIONS OF KANSAS

George D. Potts, Ph.D.

Introduction

Since the late 1960's, I have taken many students on field trips throughout Kansas. In the early years I emphasized studies of the biological communities of the state. In more recent years, I have given additional attention to geography, geology, pedology, climatology and archaeology. In order to make logical synthesis of these disciplines, I have developed a map dividing Kansas into 19 Natural Regions and 79 Subregions. Several maps have been published over the years to represent types of regions of Kansas, (i.e., general geologic maps, physiographic maps, and maps of potential vegetation). The map model that I believe best suits

this regionalization, with subunits, is the General Soil Map of Kansas.

This map is divided into 18 Land Resource Regions. Each region being divided into Soil Map Units, which total seventy nine. The Land Resource Regions being of a geological nature, and unlike vegetation regions, have boundaries that remain stable for long periods of time. The soils within the soil map units, too, maintain a relative stability. These units then, would be centers of focus for study questions related to natural communities and the various abiotic factors affecting those communities. Also, students would seek evidence of early and recent civilizations and their relationship to those biotic and abiotic components. (See Kansas Natural History Inventory outline.)

Nomenclature

The names given for the 18 Land Resource Regions of Kansas are not entirely satisfactory to me. Since the geology is the most stable component of the land, I feel a system of naming natural regions needs to be consistent with a major geological feature of the region. Names such as prairie and cross timbers represent biological communities, which are transitory and thereby do not represent long term stability, as do geological features. I prefer to simplify the topographical names, and therefore use the terms plains, hills and plateau. Where possible I name the natural region after a significant geological formation. For example, the Dakota Sandstone Hills for the Dakota Formation, whose sandstones are quite evident in that region. I divided the Chalk or Limestone Hills Land Resource Region into two natural regions, Niobrara Chalk Hills, after the prominent Niobrara chalk, and the Greenhorn Limestone Hills for the distinct Greenhorn limestone (or more popularly "Fencepost Limestone")

The name Ogallala Plains was chosen to replace the High Plains name. The Ogallala Formation is the consequence of Rocky Mountain erosion filling valleys and covering the hills of the western third of Kansas over the past 5 million years. This silt, sand, and gravel has left an expansive plain. The Sandy Ogallala Natural Region, south of the Arkansas River, is covered with sand dunes. A thick undulant covering of "floury" loess and ravines are apparent in the in the Loess Breaks and Plains Natural Region. The Gypsum Hills and the Red Plains have in common the Permian red shales, but differ in topographical relief. The Ireland Sandstone member of the Douglas Formation caps the Ireland Sandstone Hills (Chautauqua Hills) Natural Region. The escarpment/vale topography is conspicuous in the Shale and Limestone Hills (Osage Cuestas) Natural Region, which contrast in relief with the Cherokee Plains Natural Region (named after the Cherokee Formation). Fifty square miles of the Ozark Plateau bites into the southeast corner of the state,

thus that area was named the Ozark Plateau Natural Region. In addition to the Shale and Limestone Hills, the names of six other Land Resource Regions meet the geological criteria, and thus the names were changed only by substituting Natural Region for Land Resource Region. Those are the: Great Bend Sandy Plains (for the sand dunes below the great bend of the Arkansas River); Central Loess Plains (for the thick eolian deposited “glacial flour” of the area); Central Outwash Plains (where alluvial debris from Pleistocene glaciers is found below the surface); Loess and Till Hills (where the Pleistocene alluvial debris is obvious at the surface); Flint Hills (named for the numerous chert/flint nodules imbedded in the Permian limestone); Deep Loess Hills (in the northeast corner of the state, where the loess deposits are very thick), and the Terrace and Flood Plains (the dendritic river tracts of the state) Natural Regions. The Subregion names remain entirely consistent with the seventy nine Soil Map Unit names.

The 19 Natural Regions

- A. Ogallala Plains Natural Region (High Plains Land Resource Region)
 - Includes Soil Map Units 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, & 8
- B. Sandy Ogallala Plains Natural Region (Sandy High Plains Land Resource Region)
 - Includes Soil Map Units 9, 10, 11, & 12
- C. Loess Breaks and Plains Natural Region (Rolling Plains and Breaks Land Resource Region)
 - Includes Soil Map Units 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, & 21
- D. Niobrara Chalk Hills Natural Region (Chalk or Limestone Hills Land Resource Region)
 - Includes Soil Map Units 22 & 6 (Soils in units 22 and 6 have characteristics of chalk flats and chalk hills, therefore they have been put into a separate natural region)
- E. Greenhorn Limestone Hills Natural Region (Chalk or Limestone Hills Land Resource Region)
 - Includes Soil Map Units 23 & 24
- F. Dakota Sandstone Hills Natural Region (Sandstone Hills Land Resource Region)
 - Includes Soil Map Units 35, 36, & 37
- G. Great Bend Sandy Plains Natural Region (Great Bend Sandy Plains Land Resource Region)
 - Includes Soil Map Units 25, 26 & 27
- H. Gypsum Hills Natural Region (Rolling Red Plains Land Resource Region)
 - Includes Soil Map Units 28, 29, 30, & 31
- I. Red Plains Natural Region (Rolling Red Prairies Land Resource Region)
 - Includes Soil Map Units 32, 33, & 34
- J. Central Loess Plains Natural Region (Central Loess Plains Land

Resource Region)

- Includes Soil Map Units 38, 39, 40, 41, & 42

K. Central Outwash Plains Natural Region (Central Outwash Plains Land Resource Region)

- Includes Soil Map Units 43, 44, 45, & 46

L. Flint Hills Natural Resource Region (Flint Hills Land Resource Region)

- Includes Soil Map Units 53, 54, & 55

M. Loess and Till Hills Natural Region (Loess and Till Hills Land Resource Region)

- Includes Soil Map Units 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, & 52

N. Deep Loess Hills Natural Region (Deep Loess Hills Land Resource Region)

- Includes Soil Map Units 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, & 66

O. Shale and Limestone Hills Natural Region (Shale and Limestone Hills Land Resource Region)

- Includes Soil Map Units 57, 58, 59, & 60

P. Ireland Sandstone Hills Natural Region (Cross Timbers Land Resource Region)

- Includes Soil Map Unit 56

Q. Cherokee Plains Natural Region (Cherokee Prairies Land Resource Region)

- Includes Soil Map Units 67, 68, 69, & 70

R. Ozark Plateau Natural Region (Ozark Highlands Land Resource Region)

- Includes Soil Map Unit 71

S. Terrace and Flood Plains Natural Regions (Terrace and Flood Plains Land Resource Regions)

- Includes Soil Map Units 72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 77, 78, & 79

() - Land Resource Regions from General Soil Map of Kansas (1989)

Soils and Biocommunities

The soil descriptions for the Natural Regions were taken from the General Soil Map of Kansas (1989). Other soil descriptions were taken from Lauver (1989).

The potential plant associations shown in this guide were determined through field studies by plant scientists from the Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS). For each Subregion the predominant plants are listed according to percent biomass. The Natural Region and Subregion biocommunities were named after the most predominant vegetation (see Format for explanation). This Natural Region Biocommunity model illustrates the prairie communities as they may have been at the turn of the 19th century, when woody plants were controlled by frequent fires, and when grasses and forbs were repeatedly grazed by

native herbivores. Additional entries, particularly woody plants and special biocommunities, were taken from Kuchler (1974) and Lauver (1989). Special communities are described (Lauver, 1989) in some, but not all, of the Natural Regions that they are found in (i.e., Sinks and Basins in the Loess Breaks and Hills Natural Region). Extended descriptions of woodland and forest communities in the eastern Natural Regions of the state were taken from Lauver (1989). These represent potential communities that arise when prairie fires are prevented.

Application

Although not often realized, Kansas has tremendous natural diversity. A cognitive realization of this occurred to student's who have accompanied me on field trips throughout the years. Even more important, learning has occurred in the affective domain, in that students have gotten "turned on" to our natural heritage. I have observed that their awareness has turned into action to preserve and restore what nature has given us. Hopefully a regional approach, synthesizing many disciplines, will "turn on" more students in the future. This guidebook can be used, not only by students to inventory specific sites, but by state and federal agencies, and private organizations having an interest in preserving the natural heritage of Kansas.

Format

As seen on the next page, each Natural Region includes: the name of the Natural Region; the biocommunity of the Natural Region based upon the predominant vegetation, by percent biomass, in that region (percent biomass data was obtained from the Kansas Office of the NRCS); the name of the Subregion based upon dominant soil types in that unit; the biocommunity of the Subregion based upon the predominant vegetation in that unit (NRCS data); the topography and soils, and the common name, scientific name, NRCS code name and the biomass percentage of plant species (in a "normal" year) for each of the dominant soil types. (Naming of Subregion biocommunities was obtained by summing the biomass percentages for the soil components in the subregion, the plant species with the highest sum was used as the name of the biocommunity, i. e., little bluestem biomass percentages for Colby and Ulysses soil members were respectively 30% & 5%, thus the highest total for the plants in that Subregion. The species with the highest Subregion total was used as the name of the Natural Region biocommunity. If two or more species tied for the highest total than all those species were used in the biocommunity name.)

N - Not listed

P - Listed, but biomass % not given

Subregion # / Soil Map Unit #

A. OGALLALA PLAINS NATURAL REGION

Blue Grama Prairie*

1/1. Colby-Ulysses Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to steep, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Colby soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 6 to 35 percent. The deep, well drained Ulysses soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 6 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 30-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 15-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 10-20
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-20
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDAS N-5
 Small soapweed (*Yucca glauca*) YUGL 5-N
 Needle and thread (*Stipa comata*) STCO4 N-20
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX N-10
 Green needlegrass (*Stipa viridula*) STV14 N-5

2/2. Keith-Ulysses Subregion (Blue Grama-Western Wheatgrass Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Keith soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep well drained Ulysses soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 5-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 10-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 20-20
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDAS 10-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 20-20

Needle and thread (*Stipa comata*) STCO4 10-20
 Sedge (*Carex sp.*) CAREX 5-10

3/3. Ulysses-Colby Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Ulysses soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 6 percent. The deep, well drained Colby soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 5-30
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS N-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-15
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 20-10
 Buffalo grass (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDAS 5-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 20-10
 Small soapweed (*Yucca glauca*) YUGL N-5
 Needle and thread (*Stipa comata*) STCO4 20-N
 Sedge (*Carex sp.*) CAREX 10-N
 Green Needlegrass (*Stipa viridula*) STV14 5-N

4/4. Manter-Ulysses Subregion (Western Wheatgrass Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, loamy and silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Manter soil is formed in loamy, eolian sediments. It has a fine sandy loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately rapidly permeable fine sandy loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The deep well drained Ulysses soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Prairie Sandreed (*Calamovilfa longifolia*) CALO 15-N
 Little Bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 5-5
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 10-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 N-20
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDAS N-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 7-20
 Needle and thread (*Stipa comata*) STCO4 N-20
 Sedge (*Carex sp.*) CAREX N-10
 Green Needlegrass (*Stipa viridula*) STV14 N-5
 Sandhill Sage (*Artemisia filifolia*) ARFI2 5-N

Needlegrass (*Stipa sp.*) STIFA 10-N
 Squirreltail (*Sitanion hystrix*) SIHY 13-N

5/5. Colby-Kim Subregion (Blue Grama Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Colby soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 15 percent. The deep, well drained Kim soil is formed in loamy sediments. It has a clay loam surface layer about 6 inches thick and a moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 10 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 30-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 15-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 10-55
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDAS N-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-7
 Small soapweed (*Yucca glauca*) YUGL 5-N

6/7. Richfield-Ulysses Subregion (Blue Grama Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Richfield soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and a moderately slowly drained silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Ulysses soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 6 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 15-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 5-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 15-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 20-20
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDAS 10-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGBM 15-20
 Needle and thread (*Stipa comata*) STCO4 N-20
 Sedge (*Carex sp.*) CAREX N-10
 Green needlegrass (*Stipa viridula*) STV14 N-5

7/8. Ulysses-Drummond Subregion (Alkali Sacaton-Prairie Cordgrass Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping silty soils on uplands and low terraces. The deep, well drained Ulysses soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 6 percent. The deep, somewhat poorly drained Drummond soil is formed in alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 2 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Prairie cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*) SPPE N-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC N-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAV12 5-10
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-N
 Alkali sacaton (*Sporobolus airoides*) SPAI 25-5
 Inland saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata stricta*) DISPS2 5-10
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 20-5
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloide*) BUDA 5-N
 Sedge (*Carex languginosa*) CAREXLA 5-N
 Vine Mesquite (?) PADB N-5
 Sunflower (*Helianthus sp.*) HELIA3 N-5
 Illinois bundleflower (*Desmanthus illinoensis*) DEIL N-5
 Heath Aster (*Aster ericoides*) ASER 5-N

Broad, shallow area also known as the Alakali Sacaton Prairie of the Scott-Finney depression (Kuchler, 1974). Salt Flat Mixed Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

* Northern and Southern Grama-Buffalograss Prairies, and Wheatgrass-Grama-Buffalograss Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Northern and Southern Shortgrass Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

B. SANDY OGALLALA PLAINS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Blue Grama Prairie*

8/9. Manter-Satanta Subregion (Blue Grama Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately sloping, loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Manter soil is formed in loamy, eolian sediments. It has a fine sandy loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately rapidly permeable fine sandy loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The deep, well drained Satanta soil is formed in loamy, eolian sediments. It has a loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Prairie sandreed (*Calamovilfa longifolia*) CALO N-25
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 5-10
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 10-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 15-20
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) KGSM 7-5
 Sandhill sagebrush (*Artemisia filifolia*) ARFI2 5-N
 Needlegrass (*Stipa sp.*) STIPA 10-N
 Squirreltail (*Sytanean hystrix*) SIHY 13-N
 Needle and thread (*Stipa comata*) STCO N-20
 Sandhill plum (*Prunus angustifolia*) PRAN P-P

9/10. Tivoli-Vona Subregion (Blue Grama Prairie)

Rolling to hummocky, sandy soils on uplands. The deep, excessively drained Tivoli soil is formed in sandy, eolian sediments. It has a fine sand surface layer and a substratum with rapid permeability. Slopes range from 5 to 30 percent. The deep, somewhat excessively drained Vona soil is formed in loamy eolian sediments. It has a loamy fine sand surface layer about 8 inches thick and a rapidly permeable sandy loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 12 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Prairie sandreed (*Calamovilfa longifolia*) CALO N-5
 Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA 20-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-5
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 5-10
 Sand lovegrass (*Eragrostris trichodes*) ERTR3 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-20
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 N-40
 Texas bluegrass (*Poa arachnifera*) POAR 10-N
 Sandhill sagebrush (*Artemisia filifolia*) ARFI2 5-N
 Big sandreed (*Calamovilfa gigantea*) CAGI3 10-N
 Scribner's panicum (*Panicum scribnerianum*) PASC5-X 5-N
 Lespedeza (*Lespedeza sp.*) LESPE 5-N
 Sedge (*Carex sp.*) CAREX N-5
 Thickspike wheatgrass (*Agropyron ?*) AGDA
 Sandhill plum (*Prunus angustifolia*) PRAN P-P

10/11. Otero-Lincoln Subregion (Blue Grama Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately steep, loamy and sandy soils on uplands and flood plains. The deep, well drained Otero soil is formed in loamy, eolian sediments. It has a loamy fine sand surface layer about 6 inches thick and moderately rapidly permeable sandy loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 20 percent. The deep, somewhat excessively drained Lincoln soil is formed in sandy alluvium. It has a loamy fine sand surface layer about 11 inches thick and a rapidly permeable sand substratum. Slopes

range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-15
 Prairie sandreed (*Calamovilfa longifolia*) CALO 2-N
 Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA N-15
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 5-2
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-30
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 20-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-N
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 40-N
 Texas bluegrass (*Poa arachnifera*) POAR N-5
 Beaked panicum (*Panicum anceps*) PAAN N-5
 Purpletop (*Tridens flavus*) TRFL2 N-5
 Maximilian sunflower (*Helianthus maximiliani*) HEMA N-5
 Goldenrod (*Solidago sp.*) SOLID N-5
 Heath aster (*Aster ericoides*) ASER3 N-5
 Sandhill sagebrush (*Artemisia filifolia*) ARFI2 5-N
 Needlegrass (*Stipa sp.*) STIPA 10-N
 Galleta (?) HIJA 10-N
 Sandhill plum (*Prunus angustifolia*) PRAN P-P

11/12. Dalhart-Vona Subregion (Blue Grama Prairie)

Nearly level to undulating, loamy and sandy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Dalhart soil is formed in loamy, eolian sediments. It has a loamy fine sand surface layer about 5 inches thick and a moderately permeable sandy clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, somewhat excessively drained Vona soil is formed in loamy, eolian sediments. It has a loamy fine sand surface layer about 8 inches thick and a rapidly permeable sandy loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 12 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-N
 Prairie sandreed (*Calamovilfa longifolia*) CALO N-5
 Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA 20-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 5-N
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 5-10
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 20-20
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 10-40
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA 5-N
 Catclaw sensitivebrier (*Schrankia nutalii*) SCNU 3-N
 Bigtop dalia (*Dalea enneandra*) DAEN 2-N
 Sedge (*Carex sp.*) CAREX N-5

Thickspike wheatgrass (*Agropyron ?*) AGDA N-5
 Sandhill plum (*Prunus angustifolia*) PRAN P-P

* Sandsage Bluestem-Sandreed-Sagebrush Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Southern Shortgrass Prairie and Sandsage Steppe (Lauver, 1989).

C. LOESS BREAKS AND PLAINS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie*

12/13. Uly-Holdrege Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Uly soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 20 percent. The deep, well drained Holdrege soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 6 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Prairie sandreed (*Calamovilfa longifolia*) CALO 0-25
 Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 25-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-15
 Sand bluestem (*Andropogon halii*) ANHA N-10
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-N
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 10-15
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-5
 Sedge CAREX (*Carex sp.*) CAREX 5-N
 Needle and thread (*Stipa comata*) STCO4 N-20

13/14. Holdrege-Uly Subregion (Big Bluestem-Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to to moderately sloping silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Holdrege soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 6 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Uly soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-N
 Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-25
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-25
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 5-N

Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-10
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 10-10
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA 5-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-10
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-5

14/15. Uly-Penden Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Uly soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The deep, well drained Penden soil is formed in calcareous, loamy sediments. It has a clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 20 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-5
 Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 25-40
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-10
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 10-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-5
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 N-5

15/16. Holdrege-Harney Subregion (Big Bluestem-Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Holdridge soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 6 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The deep, well drained Harney soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-N
 Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-20
 Little Bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-10
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 10-5
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA 5-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-10
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N

16/17. Harney-Penden Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Harney soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Penden soil is formed in calcareous, loamy sediments. It has a clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 20 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-5
 Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-40
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-10
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR 5-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-5
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 N-5

17/18. Harney-Crete Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Harney soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 4 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Crete soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 2 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-15
 Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPCR N-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-N
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR 5-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-5
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX N-5
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 N-10

18/19. Harney-Uly Subregion (Big Bluestem-Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Harney soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Uly

soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-25
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-25
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-10
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-10
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-10

19/20. Harney Subregion (Big Bluestem-Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Harney soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 6 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10

20/21. Harney-Spearville Subregion (Blue Grama Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Harney soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Spearville soil is formed in loess. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-5
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-15
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-35
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA N-15
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-10
 Western ragweed (*Ambrosia pylostachya*) AMPS N-5

• Sinks and Basins

“These communities occupy nearly level depressions of sink holes and basins. Sinkholes are depressions caused by the collapse of the roofs of caves; the collapse occurs by the solution of rocksalt, rock gypsum, anhydrite or other soluble material by percolating underground water as either descending groundwater or artesian water (Schoewe, 1949). Basins, such as Big and Little Basin in western Clark County, owe their origin to solution and subsequent subsidence (Schowe, 1948) or as in the case with Cheyenne Bottoms (in Barton County), may be formed by structural movement in the subsurface (Kansas Biological Survey and Kansas Geological Survey, 1987). Other basins, such as the numerous saucer-shaped and shallow depressions that dot the surface across the High Plains physiographic province, have been formed by the combined action of buffalo grazing behavior and wind erosion (Darton, 1915), by impounded rainwater that percolates downward and causes unconsolidated materials to settle appreciably beneath the original shallow basins, or by the uneven distribution of sediments at the time of deposition (Schoewe, 1949). (Taken from Lauer, 1989).”

“Soils are deep to moderately deep loams and clay loams and usually contain a dense clay subsoil layer. Shallow ponds often form after large rainfall events due to poor drainage and are subject to natural drawdown/replenishment cycles during the year. The duration and frequency of flooding is subject to great fluctuation since the variability in the amount and seasonal distribution of rainfall is high (Lauer, 1989).”

“Since plant species composition fluctuates in response to the changing moisture conditions, seasonal monitoring of occurrences is necessary to develop an understanding of the plant-moisture dynamics (Lauer, 1989).”
Dominant species of these special biocommunities may include:

- Cattails (*typha angustifolia*)
- Bulrushes (*Scirpus* spp)
- Spikerushes (*Eleocharis* spp)
- Saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*)

Annual species which may be absent to common (depending on moisture conditions) include:

- Kochia (*Kochia scoparia*)
- Saltmarsh aster (*Aster subulatus*)
- Chenopods (*Chenopodium* spp)
- Pigweeds (*Amaranthus* spp)
- Sea-blite (*Suaeda depressa*)

* Northern and Southern Bluestem-Grama Prairies (Kuchler, 1974). Loess

Breaks Mixed Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

D. NIOBRARA CHALK HILLS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie*

21/22. Harney-Wakeen-Brownell Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep well drained Harney soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 3 percent. The moderately deep well drained Wakeen soil is formed in material weathered from chalky limestone. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 2 to 15 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Brownell soil is formed in material weathered from chalky limestone. It has a gravelly loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable very gravelly loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 2 to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation for this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-35-40
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-5-N
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-N-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-15-20
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-N-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron curtipendula*) AGSM 10-N-N

22/6. Ulysses-Elkader Subregion (Western Wheatgrass-Alkali Sacaton-Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Ulysses soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 8 percent. The deep, well drained Elkader soil is formed in silty material weathered from chalky limestone and shale. It has a silt loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from about 1 to 6 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE N-15
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC N-25

Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 5-N
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-15
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-10
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA 5-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 20-5
 Alkali sacaton (*Sporobulus airoides*) SPAI 25-N
 Inland saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*) DISPS2 5-N
 Heath aster (*Aster ericoides*) ASER N-5

* Chalkflat Bluestem-Grama-Saltgrass Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Chalkflat Mixed Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

E. GREENHORN LIMESTONE HILLS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie*

23/23. Harney-Corinth-Bogue Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, silty and clayey soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Harney soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 3 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Corinth soil is formed in material weathered from calcareous shale. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 1 to 3 percent. The moderately deep, moderately well drained Bogue soil is formed in material weathered from acid shale. It has a clay surface layer about 6 inches thick and very slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 15 percent. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-40-40
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-5-N
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-5-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-10-15
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-N-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-5-N
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 N-5-10

24/24. Harney-Wakeen-Nibson Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to steep, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Harney soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 3 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Wakeen soil is formed in material weathered from chalky limestone. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 2 to 15 percent. The shallow, well drained Nibson soil is formed in material weathered from chalky shale and soft limestone. It has a silt loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 15 inches. Slopes range from 5 to 25 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-35-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-5-N
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-N-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-15-20
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-5-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AMCA6 10-N-5

* The Northern Bluestem-Grama Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Northern Mixed Prairie (Lauver, 1989)

F. DAKOTA SANDSTONE HILLS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie*

25/35. Lancaster-Hedville Subregion (Big Bluestem-Little Bluestem Prairie)

Moderately sloping to steep, loamy soils on uplands. The moderately deep, well drained Lancaster soil is formed in material weathered from sandstone and sandy shale. It has a loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 7 percent. The shallow, somewhat excessively drained Hedville soil is formed in material weathered from sandstone. It has a stony loam surface layer about 14 inches thick over sandstone bedrock. It has moderate permeability. Slopes range from 5 to 25 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-35
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-5

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5

26/36. Crete-Lancaster Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately steep, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Crete soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Lancaster soil is formed in material weathered from sandstone and sandy shale. It has a loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 7 percent. The shallow, somewhat excessively drained Headville soil is formed in material weathered from sandstone. It has a stony loam surface layer about 14 inches thick over sandstone bedrock. It has moderate permeability. Slopes range from 5 to 20 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 5-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 10-N
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N

27/37. Geary-Wells Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Geary soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 7 percent. The deep, well drained Wells soil is formed in loamy, old alluvium. It has a loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-25
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Sideoats grama BOCU (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) 5-5
 Tall dropseed SPAS (*Sporobolus asper*) 5-5

Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX N-5
 Missouri goldenrod (*Solidago missouriensis*) SOMI N-5

* Dakota Sandstone Bluestem-Grama Prairie. The transition between the Bluestem-Grama Prairie and the Bluestem prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Dakota Hills Tallgrass Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

G. GREAT BEND SANDY PLAINS (DRAFT)

Sand Bluestem Prairie*

28/25. Pratt-Tivoli Subregion (Sand Bluestem-Little Bluestem Prairie)

Undulating to hummocky, sandy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Pratt soil is formed in sandy, eolian sediments. It has a loamy fine sand surface layer about 12 inches thick and a rapidly permeable loamy fine sand subsoil. Slopes range from 2 to 12 percent. The deep, excessively drained Tivoli soil is formed in sandy, eolian sediments. It has a fine sand surface layer and substratum with rapid permeability. Slopes range from 5 to 30 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA 25-20
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 5-N
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONO2 10-N
 Sand lovegrass (*Eragrostis trichodes*) ERTR3 10-5
 Big sandreed (*Calamovilfa arachnifera*) CAGI3 N10
 Scribner's panicum (*Panicum scribnerianum*) PASC5
 Texas bluegrass (*Poa arachnifera*) POAR N-10
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 5-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR 5-N
 Lespedeza (*Lespedeza* sp.) LESP N-5
 Sand sagebrush (*Artemisia filifolia*) ARFI N-5

29/26. Shellabarger-Albion Subregion (Sand Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Shellabarger soil is formed in loamy old alluvium. It has a sandy loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a moderately permeable sandy clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 12 percent. The deep, somewhat excessively drained Albion soil is formed in loamy and sandy sediments. It has a sandy loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately rapidly permeable sandy loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 10-N
 Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA 25-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SUNO2 10-10
 Sand lovegrass (*Eragrostis trichodes*) ERTR3 5-5

30/27. Naron-Farnum Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Naron soil is formed in loamy, eolian sediments. It has a fine sandy loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable sandy clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 4 percent. The deep, well drained Farnum soil is formed in loamy, old alluvium. It has a loam surface layer about 14 inches thick and moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 6 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-20
 Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA 10-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5

• Sandhill Pools

“Nearly level to gently sloping bottomland areas between undulating to hummocky sand dunes. Soils are deep, sandy and sandy loams formed in sandy eolian sediments, and are poorly drained since they contain a relatively impervious subsoil. These areas are usually flooded for part or all of the year because of poor drainage and a seasonally high water table. The duration and frequency of flooding is related to the amount and seasonal distribution of rainfall. Some occurrences may vanish during years of low precipitation, but may reappear given sufficient moisture conditions during subsequent years (Lauver, 1989).”
 The predominant vegetation of these special biocommunities are:

Broad-leaved cattail (*Typha latifolia*)
 Hardstem bulrush (*Scirpus acutus*)
 Arrowhead (*Sagittaria* sp.)
 Waterthread pondweed (*Potamogeton diversifolius*)
 Illinois pondweed (*Potamogeton illinoensis*)
 Longleaf pondweed (*Potamogeton nodosus*)
 Taperleaf flatsedge (*Cyperus acuminatus*)
 Yellow nutgrass (*Cyperus esculentus*)

Flatsedge (*Cyperus odoratus*)
 Water plaintain (*Alisma triviale*)
 Needle spikeseedge (*Eleocharis acicularis*)
 Wapato arrowhead (*Sagittaria cuneata*)
 Common arrowhead (*Sagittaria latifolia*)
 Burhead (*Echinodorus rostratus*)

•Saline Marsh

“ A low lying wetland community that occupies swales and depressions of floodplains and their terraces, and valley basins. Soils are deep and very poorly drained. These soils have formed in alluvium or loess, and consist of peat, muck, or mineral materials. This community is distinguished from the freshwater marsh community by its restriction to salty seepage areas which often contain brackish or stagnant water. Dominant species of these special biocommunities include:

Inland saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*)
 Sea blite (*Sueda depressa*)
 Bulrush (*Scirpus* spp.)

* Sand Bluestem-Sandreed Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Sand Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

H. GYPSUM HILLS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Little Bluestem Prairie*

31/28. Carey-Woodward Subregion (Little Bluestem-Blue Grama Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Carey soil is formed in material weathered from red silty shale or silty sandstone. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 6 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Woodward soil is formed in material weathered from red sandstone. It has a loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and moderately permeable loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA N-20
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC N-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-10
 Canada wildrye (*Elymus canadensis*) ELCA N-5

Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS N-5
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 15-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 20-5
 Hairy grama (*Bouteloua hirsuta*) BOHI2 5-N
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA 15-N
 Plains bristlegrass (*Setaria machrostychnus*) SEMA5 5-N
 Texas needlegrass (*Stipa leucotricha*) STLE 5-N
 Arizona cottontop (*Trichachna californica*) DICA8 5-N
 Lespedeza (*Lespedeza* sp.) LESP N-5
 Vine mesquite (?) PAOB 5-N
 Dotted gayfeather (*Liatrus punctata*) LIPU 5-N

32/29. Vernon-Woodward Subregion (Sideoats Grama Prairie)

Moderately sloping to moderately steep, clayey and loamy soils on uplands. The moderately deep, well drained Vernon soil is formed in material weathered from clayey shale. It has a clay surface layer about 8 inches thick and a very slowly permeable clay subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 24 inches. Slopes range from 5 to 15 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Woodward soil is formed in material weathered from red sandstone. It has a loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 25 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA N-20
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC N-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-10
 Canada wildrye (*Elymus canadensis*) N-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS N-5
 Sand dropseed (*Sporobolus cryptandrus*) SPCR 15-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 25-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-5
 Hairy grama (*Bouteloua hirsuta*) BOHI2 5-N
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA 15-N
 Arizona cottontop (*Trichachna californica*) DICA8 5-N
 Silver bluestem (*Andropogon saccharoides*) ANSA 5-N
 Lespedeza (*Lespedeza* sp.) LESP N-5
 Vine mesquite (?) PAOB 5-N
 Dotted gayfeather (*Liatrus punctata*) LIPU N-5

33/30. Woodward-Quinlan Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, loamy soils on uplands. The moderately deep, well drained Woodward soil is formed in material weathered from red sandstone. It has a loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 1 to 6 percent. The shallow, well drained Quinlan soil is formed in material weathered from red sandstone. It has a loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately permeable loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 14 inches. Slopes range from 6 to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA 20-15
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-30
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-3
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-5
 Canada wildrye (*Elymus canadensis*) 5-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-3
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-3
 Scribner's panicum (*Panicum scribnerianum*) PASC5 N-5
 Lespedeza (*Lespedeza* sp.) LESP 5-N
 Prairie clover (*Dalea* sp.) DALEA N-5
 Dotted gayfeather (*Liatrus punctata*) LIPU 5-5

34/31. Grant-Pond Creek Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Grant soil is formed in material weathered from red silty sandstone or silty shale. It has a silt loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 6 percent. The deep, well drained Pond Creek soil is formed in material weathered from silty sandstone or silty shale. It has a silt loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Sand bluestem (*Andropogon hallii*) ANHA 20-20
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Canada wildrye (*Elymus canadensis*) 5-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-5
 Roundheaded lespedeza (*Lespedeza capitata*) LECA 2-N
 Slender lespedeza (*Lespedeza virginica*) LEVI3-N

Prairie clover (*Dalea* sp.) DALEA N-5
 Dotted gayfeather (*Liatrus punctata*) LIPU 2-5

• Scattered, or small groves of woody plants include:

Eastern red cedar (*Juniperus virginiana*)
 Hackberry (*Celtis occidentalis*)
 Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
 Soapberry (*Sapindus saponaria*)
 Green ash (*Fraxinus pennsylvanica*)
 Bur oak (*Quercus macrocarpa*)
 American elm (*Ulmus americana*)
 Sand hill plum (*Prunus angustifolia*)
 Smooth sumac (*Rhus glabra*)
 Corralberry-Buckbrush (*Symphoricarpos orbicularis*)

* Cedar Hills Bluestem-Grama-Cedar Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Red Hills Mixed Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

I. RED PLAINS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Little Bluestem Prairie*

35/32. Blanket-Farnum Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Blanket soil is formed in old alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Farnum soil is formed in loamy, old alluvium. It has a loam surface layer about 14 inches thick and moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 10-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 15-10
 Canada wildrye (*Elymus canadensis*) ELCA4 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 10-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N
 Texas needlegrass (*Stipa leucotricha*) STLE 5-N
 Silver bluestem (*Andropogon saccharoides*) BOSA 5-N

36/33. Farnum-Shellaburger Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Farnum soil is formed in loamy, old alluvium. It has a loam surface layer about 14 inches thick and moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Shellabarger soil is formed in loamy, old alluvium. It has a sandy loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable sandy loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 6 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-10
 Sand bluestem (*Andropogon Hallii*) ANHA N-25
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-N
 Sand lovegrass (*Eragrostis trichodes*) ERTR3 N-5

37/34. Bethany-Farnum Subregion (Little Bluestem-Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Bethany soil is formed in old alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Farnum soil is formed in loamy, old alluvium. It has a loam surface layer about 14 inches thick and moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 6 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Canada wildrye (*Elymus canadensis*) ELCA4 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N
 Dotted gayfeather (*Liatrus punctata*) LIPU 5-N

* Southern Bluestem-Grama Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Southern Mixed Prairie (Lauver, 1989)

J. CENTRAL LOESS PLAINS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie*

38/38. Hastings-Kipson Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Hastings soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The shallow, somewhat excessively drained Kipson soil is formed in material weathered from calcareous, silty shale. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Bedrock is at a depth of about 16 inches. Slopes range from 5 to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-5
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-5
 Porcupinegrass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-15
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N

39/39. Crete-Hastings Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Crete soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Hastings soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 10-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 5-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N
 Porcupinegrass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 10-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-5

40/40. Crete-Geary Natural Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Crete soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty

clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Geary soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-35
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 5-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 10-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N

41/41. Crete-Smolan Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to gently sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Crete soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Smolan soil is formed in loess. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-25
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 5-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Porcupinegrass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 10-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N

42/42. Crete-Mayberry Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Crete soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent.

The deep, moderately well drained Mayberry soil is formed in glacial till. It has a clay loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and a slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 2 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-20
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 5-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-10
 Porcupinegrass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 10-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Prairie dropseed (*Sporobolus heterolepis*) SPHE N-5
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-5

* Northern Low Bluestem-Grama Prairie and Southern Low Plains Bluestem-Switchgrass-Indiangrass Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Claypan Tallgrass Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

K. CENTRAL OUTWASH PLAINS NATURAL UNIT (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie*

43/43. Ladysmith-Goessel Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level, silty and clayey soils on uplands. The deep, somewhat poorly drained Ladysmith soil is formed in loamy, old alluvium. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a very slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Goessel soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silty clay surface layer about 14 inches thick and very slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-20
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5

44/44. Irwin-Clime Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Irwin soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silt clay loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a very slowly permeable subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 7 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Clime soil is formed in calcareous, clayey shale. It has a silty loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Shale is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-20
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-30
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-15
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 N-5
 New Jersey Tea (*Ceanothus herbaceus*) CEHE N-5
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 N-5

45/45. Irwin-Ladysmith Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Irwin soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silt clay loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a very slowly permeable subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 8 percent. The deep, somewhat poorly drained Ladysmith soil is formed in loamy, old alluvium. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a very slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-25
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5

46/46. Wymore-Irwin Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping or moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Wymore soil is formed in loess. It has a

silty clay loam surface layer about 6 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 4 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Irwin soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silt clay loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a very slowly permeable subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-25
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-N
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Prairie dropseed (*sporobolus heterolepsis*) SPHE 5-N
 Kentucky bluegrass (*Poa pratensis*) POPR 5-N

* Southern Low Plains Bluestem-Switchgrass-Indiangrass Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Claypan Tallgrass Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

L. FLINT HILLS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie *

47/53. Clime-Sohn Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to steep, silty soils on uplands. The moderately deep, well drained Clime soil is formed in calcareous, clayey shale. It has a silty loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Shale is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 1 to 30 percent. The shallow, somewhat excessively drained Sohn soil is formed in material weathered from limestone. It has a clay loam surface layer about 10 inches thick over limestone. Slopes range from 0 to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-15
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 30-15
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 15-25
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 5-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-5
 New Jersey Tea (*Ceanothus herbaceous*) CEHE 5-N
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 5-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS N-5

48/54. Dwight-Labette Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Dwight soil is formed in clayey sediments. It has a silt loam surface layer about 5 inches thick and a very slowly permeable, saline clay subsoil. Limestone is at a depth of about 54 inches. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Labette soil is formed in material weathered from interbedded limestone and clayey shale. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Limestone is at a depth of about 36 inches. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 15-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 10-20
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-N
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU N-15
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 5-10
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 10-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 10-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-N
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA 5-N
 Dotted gayfeather (*Liatrus punctata*) LIPU 5-N

49/55. Florence-Labette Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Moderately sloping or moderately steep, loamy and silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Florence soil is formed in material weathered from cherty limestone. It has a cherty silt loam surface layer about 11 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable very cherty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 5 to 15 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Labette soil is formed in material weathered from interbedded limestone and clayey shale. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Limestone is at a depth of about 36 inches. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-N
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-15
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N

Eastern gamagrass (*Tripsacum dactyloides*) TRDA3 5-5
 Compass plant (*Silphium laciniatum*) SILA3 N-5

* Northern & Southern Flint Hills Bluestem-Switchgrass-Indiangrass Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

M. LOESS AND TILL HILLS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie*

50/47. Wymore-Pawnee Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping or moderately sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Wymore soil is formed in loess. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 6 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Pawnee soil is formed in glacial till. It has a clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-25
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Prairie dropseed (*Sporobolus heterolepis*) SPHE 5-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 N-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Eastern gama grass (*Tripsacum dactyloides*) TRDA 5-N
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N

51/48. Tully-Pawnee Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping or moderately sloping, silty or loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Tully soil is formed in clayey colluvium. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Pawnee soil is formed in glacial till. It has a clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 40-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-25
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Prairie dropseed (*Sporobolus heterolepis*) SPHE N-5
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS N-5
 Eastern gamagrass (*Tripsacum dactyloides*) TRDA 5-N

52/49. Pawnee-Burchard Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Moderately sloping or moderately steep, loamy soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Pawnee soil is formed in glacial till. It has a clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 8 percent. The deep, well drained Burchard soil is formed in glacial till. It has a clay loam surface layer about 13 inches thick and moderately slowly permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 6 to 20 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-20
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-10
 Prairie dropseed (*Sporobolus heterolepis*) SPHE 5-5
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 N-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS N-5
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N

53/50. Grundy-Pawnee Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, somewhat poorly drained Grundy soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 7 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Pawnee soil is formed in glacial till. It has a clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE N-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC N-25
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 P-10
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Prairie dropseed (*Sporobolus heterolepis*) SPHE N-5
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 N-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS P-5
 Lead plant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 P-N
 Eastern gamagrass (*Tripsacum dactyloides*) TRDA P-N
 Prairie cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*) SPPE P-N
 Roundhead lespedeza (*Lespedeza capitata*) LECA8 P-N
 Smooth sumac (*Rhus glabra*) RHGL P-N
 Indian current coralberry (*Symphorica orbiculatus*) SYOR P-N

54/51. Marshall-Morrill Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping or moderately sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Marshall soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 13 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The deep, well drained Morrill soil is formed in glacial till. It has a loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 12 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 35-35
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 5-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-N
 Prairie dropseed (*Sporobolus heterolepis*) SPHE 5-N
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 5-N

55/52. Martin-Pawnee Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping or moderately sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Martin soil is formed in material weathered from silty and clayey shale. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The deep, moderately well

drained Pawnee soil is formed in glacial till. It has a clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15 25
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5
 Prairie dropseed (*Sporobolus heterolepis*) SPHE N-5
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 N-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 5-N
 Maximilian sunflower (*Helianthus maximiliani*) HEMA2 5-N

- Northeastern Woodland

“An open oak forest community with individual trees scattered across the landscape. This community occupies moderately sloping to steep south and west facing slopes of silty and loamy soils that have formed in loess or glacial till. Soils are deep and range from moderately well drained to well drained (Lauver, 1989).” The chief overstory dominants include:

Bur oak (*Quercus macrocarpa*)
 Post oak (*Quercus stellata*)

Understory dominants include:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*)
 Little bluestem (*Sorghastrum nutans*)

- Eastern Upland Forest

“An oak-hickory forest community that occupies gentle to moderately steep slopes on highlands and steep valley sides on silty and loamy soils. These soils have formed in loess, glacial till, or material weathered from shale or limestone. The soils are moderately deep to deep and range from somewhat poorly drained to well drained (Lauver, 1989).” The overstory dominants include:

White oak (*Quercus alba*)

Red oak (*Quercus borealis*)
 Black oak (*Quercus velutina*)
 Bitternut hickory (*Carya cordiformis*)
 Shagbark hickory (*Carya ovata*)

* Glaciated Region Bluestem-Switchgrass-Indiangrass Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Hill Prairie (Lauver 1989).

N. DEEP LOESS HILLS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie *

56/61. Martin-Vinland Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Moderately sloping to steep, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Martin soil is formed in material weathered from silty and clayey shale. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The shallow, somewhat excessively drained Vinland soil is formed in material weathered from interbedded sandy and silty shale. It has a silty loam clay surface layer about 6 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Sandy or silty shale is at a depth of about 16 inches. Slopes range from 5 to 30 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-25
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-25
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 5-N
 Maximilian sunflower (*Helianthus maximiliani*) HEMA2 5-N

57/62. Sharpsburg-Shelby Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping to moderately steep, silty and loam soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Sharpsburg soil is formed in loess. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The deep, well drained Shelby soil is formed in glacial till. It has a clay loam surface layer about 11 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3

to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-15
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5
 Kentucky bluegrass (*Poa pratensis*) POPR 5-N
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 5-5
 Maximilian sunflower (*Helianthus maximiliani*) HEMA2 N-5

58/63. Monona Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Moderately sloping or moderately steep, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Monoma soil formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 11 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 18 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 35
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5
 Porcupine grass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 5
 Prairie dropseed (*Sporobolus heterolepis*) SPHE 5
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5

59/64. Knox-Armster Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie?)

Moderately sloping and steep, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Knox soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 7 to 30 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Armster soil is formed in glacial till. It has a clay loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 20 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE P-P
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC P-P
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 P-P
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 P-P
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS N-P
 Purpletop (*Trioda flava*) TRFL2 N-P
 Roundhead lespedeza (*Lespedeza capitata*) LECA8
 Smooth Sumac (*Rhus glabra*) RHGL N-P
 Fragrant sumac (*Rhus aromatica*) SRHAR4 P-P
 Poison Ivy (*Rhus radicans*) TORA P-P
 Blackberry (*Rubus ostryifolius*) RUBUS P-P
 Indiantartan coralberry (*Symphoricarpos orbiculatus*) SYOR P-P
 Currant (*Ribes odoratum*) RIBES P-P
 Summer grape (*Vitis aestivalis*) VIAE P-P

60/65. Sharpsburg-Oska Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Gently or moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Sharpsburg soil is formed in loess. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a moderately slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Oska soil is formed in loess. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Limestone is at a depth of about 38 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 10-10
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-20
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Kentucky bluegrass (*Poa pratensis*) POPR 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-N
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 5-N
 Compass plant (*Silphium laciniatum*) SILA3 N-5

61/66. Polo-Oska Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping or moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Polo soil is formed in loess. It has a silt loam surface layer about 13 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 2 to 5 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Oska soil is formed in loess. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Limestone is at a depth of about 38 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE P-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC P-20
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 P-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 P-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS P-5
 Purpletop (*Triodia flava*) TRFL2 P-N
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA P-N
 Roundhead lespedeza (*Lespedeza capitata*) LECA P-N
 Compass plant (*Silphium laciniatum*) SILA3 N-5
 Sunflower (*Helianthus sp.*) HELA3 P-N
 Goldenrod (*Solidago sp.*) SOLID P-N
 Smooth sumac (*Rhus glabra*) RHGL
 Indiancurrant coralberry (*Symphoricarpos orbiculatus*) SYOR P-N

• Northeastern Woodland

“An open oak forest community with individual trees scattered across the landscape. This community occupies moderately sloping to steep south and west facing slopes of silty and loamy soils that have formed in loess or glacial till. Soils are deep and range from moderately well drained to well drained (Lauver, 1989).” The chief overstory dominants include:

Bur oak (*Quercus macrocarpa*)
 Post oak (*Quercus stellata*)

Understory dominants include:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*)
 Little bluestem (*Sorghastrum nutans*)

- Eastern Upland Forest

“An oak-hickory forest community that occupies gentle to moderately steep slopes on highlands and steep valley sides on silty and loamy soils. These soils have formed in loess, glacial till, or material weathered from shale or limestone. The soils are moderately deep to deep and range from somewhat poorly drained to well drained (Lauver, 1989).”
The overstory dominants include:

- White oak (*Quercus alba*)
- Red oak (*Quercus borealis*)
- Black oak (*Quercus velutina*)
- Bitternut hickory (*Carya cordiformis*)
- Shagbark hickory (*Carya ovata*)

* Northern Oak-Hickory Forest (Kuchler, 1974)

O. SHALE AND LIMESTONE HILLS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie *

62/57. Eram-Kenoma Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The moderately deep, moderately well drained Eram soil is formed in material weathered from clayey shale. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a slowly permeable clay subsoil. Shale is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Kenoma soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 6 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

- Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-25
- Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-20
- Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-15
- Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) POVI2 15-15
- Scribner's panicum (*Panicum scribnerianum*) PASC5 5-N
- Purpletop (*Triodia flava*) TRFL2 5-N
- Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
- Catclaw sensitive brier (*Schrankia nuttali*) SCUN 5-N
- Goldenrod (*Solidago* sp.) SOLID 5-N
- Sideoatas grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5

63/58. Kenoma-Martin Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping or moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Kenoma soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 6 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Martin soil is formed in material weathered from silty and clayey shale. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 25-30
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-15
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 15-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) POVI2 15-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-5
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 N-5
 Maximilian sunflower (*Helianthus maximiliani*) HEMA2 N-5

64/59. Eram-Lula Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The moderately deep, moderately well drained Eram soil is formed in material weathered from clayey shale. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a slowly permeable clay subsoil. Shale is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 1 to 8 percent. The deep, well drained Lula soil formed in material weathered from limestone. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Limestone is at a depth of about 50 inches. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-35
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Scribner's panicum (*Panicum scribnerianum*) PASC5 5-5
 Purpletop (*Triodia flava*) TRFL2 5-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Catclaw sensitivebrier (*Schrakia nuttali*) SCUN 5-5
 Goldenrod (*Solidago* sp.) SOLID 5-5

65/60. Woodson-Kenoma Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level or gently sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, somewhat poorly drained Woodson soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a very slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 2 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Kenoma soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 6 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 35-25
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-20
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 15-15
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) POVI2 15-15
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5

• Limestone Glade

“This community occupies nearly level to steep upland south- or west-facing slopes and bluffs of dissected hills and valleys. Soils have formed in material weathered from limestone, and are shallow, rocky, well drained and usually clayey. Exposed horizontal layers of limestone (i.e. outcrops) are common to abundant. Vegetation is dominated by grasses with a mixture of calciphilic and prairie species (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant species are:

Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*)
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*)

• Eastern Upland Forest

“An oak-hickory forest community that occupies gentle to moderately steep slopes on highlands and steep valley sides on silty and loamy soils. These soils have formed in loess, glacial till, or material weathered from shale or limestone. The soils are moderately deep to deep and range from somewhat poorly drained to well drained (Lauver, 1989).” The overstory dominants include:

White oak (*Quercus alba*)
 Red oak (*Quercus borealis*)
 Black oak (*Quercus velutina*)
 Bitternut hickory (*Carya cordiformis*)
 Shagbark hickory (*Carya ovata*)

* Osage Cuesta Bluestem Switchgrass-Indiangrass Prairie (Kuchler, 1974).
Claypan Tallgrass Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

P. IRELAND SANDSTONE HILLS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Post Oak-Blackjack Oak-Big Bluestem Cross Timbers*

66/56. Steedman-Niotaze-Stephenville Subregion(Post Oak-Blackjack Oak-Big Bluestem Savanna)

Moderately sloping to steep, loamy soils on uplands. The moderately deep, moderately well drained Steedman soil is formed in material weathered from clayey shale. It has a stony loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and a slowly permeable clay subsoil. Shale is at a depth of about 30 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 20 percent. The moderately deep, somewhat poorly drained Niotaze soil is formed in material weathered from interbedded clayey shale and sandstone. It has a cobbly fine sandy loam surface layer about 3 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Shale is at a depth of about 28 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 40 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Stephenville soil is formed in material weathered from sandstone. It has a fine sandy loam surface layer about 4 inches thick and a moderately permeable sandy clay loam subsoil. Sandstone is at a depth of about 34 inches. Slopes range from 3 to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 25-25-25
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-20-20
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-5-5
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-5-5
 Purpletop (*Triodia flava*) TRFL2 N-5-5
 Canada wildrye (*Elymus canadensis*) ELCA4 5-N-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) COCU 5-N-N
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-N-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N-N
 Sand lovegrass (*Eragrostes trichodes*) ERTR3 N-N-5
 Scribner's panicum (*Panicum scribnerianum*) PASC5 N-N-5
 Lespedeza (*Lespedeza* sp.) LESPE 5-N-N
 Dotted gayfeather (*Liatrus punctata*) LIPU N-N-5
 Hairy sunflower (*Helianthus hirsutus*) HEHI2 N-5-N
 Sunflower (*Helianthus* sp.) HELIA3 N-N-5
 Goldenrod (*Solidago* sp.) SOLID N-N-5
 Post oak (*Quercus marilandica*) QUST N-10-N
 Blackjack oak (*Quercus stellata*) QUMA3 N-10-N

- Other tree species include:

- Black oak (*Quercus velutina*)
- Dwarf chinkapin oak (*Quercus prinoides*)
- Bitternut hickory (*Carya cordiformis*)

- Sandstone Glade

“This community occupies gently rolling plains, gentle to moderately steep slopes of hills and knobs, and the steeper upper slopes of south-facing escarpments. Soils have formed in material weathered from sandstone, and are shallow, sandy, and rapidly drained with vernal inundated depressions. Level massive areas of bedrock and widely interspersed rock fragments or boulders are often exposed on the soil surface (Lauver, 1989).” Vegetation in this special biocommunity is dominated by:

- Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*)
- Butlers quillwort (*Isoetes butleri*)

Also:

- Stunted xerophytic trees and shrubs
- Mosses and lichens abundant on undisturbed bare rock

* Oak-Bluestem Forest (Cross Timbers) (Kuchler, 1974). Cross Timbers Woodland (Lauver, 1989).

Q. CHEROKEE PLAINS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie *

67/67. Dennis-Bates Subregion(Big Bluestem Prairie)

Gently sloping or moderately sloping, silty and loamy soils on uplands. The deep, moderately well drained Dennis soil is formed in material weathered from shale. It has a silt loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Bates soil is formed in material weathered from sandstone. It has a loam surface layer about 9 inches thick and a moderately permeable clay loam subsoil. Sandstone is at a depth of about 33 inches. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

- Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 35-35
- Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSS 10-25
- Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU 10-10
- Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 15-10
- Scribner’s panicum (*Panicum scribnerianum*) PASC5 5-N
- Purpletop (*Triodia flava*) TRFL2 5-N
- Catclaw sensitivebrier (*Schrankia nuttalli*) SCUN 5-N
- Goldenrod (*Solidag* sp.) SOLID 5-N

68/68. Parsons-Dennis Subregion (Big Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately sloping, silty soils on uplands. The deep, somewhat poorly drained Parsons soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a very slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 2 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Dennis soil is formed in material weathered from shale. It has a silt loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 1 to 7 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-35
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 15-15
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-N
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS N-5
 Scribner's panicum (*Panicum scribnerianum*) PASC5 N-5
 Purpletop (*Triodia flava*) TRFL2 N-5
 Catclaw sensitivebrier (*Schrankia nuttalli*) SCUN N-5
 Goldenrod (*Solidag* sp) SOLID N-5
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA 5-N
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 5-N
 Illinois bundleflower (*Desmanthus illinoensis*) DEIL 2-N
 Goldenrod (*Solidago* sp) SOLID 5-N
 Indiancurrent coralberry (*Symphoricarpos orbiculatus*) SYOR 5-N

69/69. Kanima-Parsons Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to steep, silty soils and strip mine soils on uplands. The deep, well drained Kanima soil is formed in strip mine spoil. It has a shaley silty clay loam surface layer and a moderately permeable extremely shaley silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 3 to 50 percent.

The deep, somewhat poorly drained Parsons soil is formed in clayey, old alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a very slowly permeable clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 2 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 15-20
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 15-25

Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 N-15
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 N-5
 Purpletop (*Tridens flavus*) TRFL2 5-N
 Buffalograss (*Buchloe dactyloides*) BUDA N-5
 Leadplant (*Amorpha canescens*) AMCA6 N-3
 Illinois bundleflower (*Desmanthus illinoensis*) DEIL N-2
 Goldenrod (*Solidago* sp.) SOLID N-5
 Indianturrent coralberry (*Symphoricarpos orbiculatus*) N-5
 Eastern cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*) PODE3 15-N
 Black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) ROPS 10-N
 Hackberry (*Celtis occidentalis*) CEOC 5-N
 Winged elm (*Ulmus* ?) ULAL 5-N
 American Sycamore (*Platanus occidentalis*) PLOC 5-N

70/70. Catoosa-Clareson Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Nearly level to moderately steep, silty soils on uplands. The moderately deep, well drained Catoosa soil is formed in material weathered from limestone. It has a silt loam surface layer about 10 inches thick and a moderately permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The moderately deep, well drained Clareson soil is formed in material weathered from limestone. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 8 inches thick and a slowly permeable flaggy silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 15 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 20-15
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 25-30
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-10
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-5
 Canada wildrye (*Elymus canadensis*) ELCA4 5-N
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU 5-15
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 5-N
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-5
 Lespedeza (*Lespedeza* sp.) LESPE 5-N
 Dotted gayfeather (*Liatrus punctatus*) LTPU 5-N

* Cherokee Plain Bluestem-Switchgrass-Indiangrass Prairie (Kuchler, 1974). Claypan Tallgrass Prairie (Lauver, 1989).

R. OZARK PLATEAU NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Little Bluestem Prairie *

71/71. Clarksville-Nixa Subregion (Little Bluestem Prairie)

Moderately sloping to steep, cherty silty soils on uplands. The deep, somewhat excessively drained Clarkson soil is formed in material weathered from cherty limestone. It has a cherty silt loam surface layer about 4 inches thick and a moderately rapidly permeable extremely cherty silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 10 to 30 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Nixa soil is formed in material weathered from cherty limestone. It has a cherty silt loam surface layer about 5 inches thick and a very slowly permeable extremely cherty silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 2 to 9 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE N-15
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC N-25
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 N-10
 Panicum (*Panicum* sp.) PANIC N-10
 Lespedeza (*Lespedeza* sp.) LESPE N-5
 Purpletop (*Triodia flava*) TRFL2 N-5

• Ozark Upland Forest

“An oak-hickory forest community that occupies nearly level to steep slopes on uplands of cherty, silty soils. The soils are deep (bedrock is at a depth of about 60 inches below the subsoils) and contain a relatively cherty silt loam surface over a cherty silt loam subsoil. The soils are somewhat excessively drained to moderately well drained, and have formed in material weathered from cherty limestone (Lauver, 1989).”

The dominant tree species are:

White oak (*Quercus alba*)
 Bitternut hickory (*Carya cordiformis*)
 Shagbark hickory (*Carya ovata*)

Common to abundant species include:

Flowering dogwood (*Cornus florida*)
 Poverty oatgrass (*Danthonia spicata*)

* Ozark Forest (Kuchler, 1974).

S. TERRACE AND FLOODPLAINS NATURAL REGION (DRAFT)

Big Bluestem Prairie *

72/72. Las Animas-Bridgeport Subregion (Arkansas River-West) - Big

Bluestem Prairie

Nearly level, loamy and silty soils on floodplains. The deep, somewhat poorly drained Los Animas soil is formed in calcareous, loamy, recent alluvium. It has a sandy loam surface layer about 6 inches thick and a moderately rapidly permeable sandy loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Bridgeport soil is formed in calcareous, silty, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 12 inches thick and moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 10-35
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 5-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 5-15
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX () 10-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 10-10
 Prairie cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*) SPPE 10-N
 Kentucky bluegrass (*Poa pratensis*) POPR 5-N
 Slender wheatgrass (*Agropyron pauciflorum*) AGTR 10-N
 Plains bluegrass (*Poa arida*) LPOAR3 5-N

- Western Low Prairie

“A native lowland grassland community that occupies nearly level soils on floodplains along rivers, streams, and creeks. Soils are deep, poorly drained, and have formed in alluvium. these soils are nearly always saturated with water, or are seasonally inundated with surface water during the winter and/or spring seasons (Lauver, 1989).” Dominant plants include:

Prairie cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*)
 Sedges (*Carex* spp.)

- Western Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies nearly level, loamy, silty, and sandy soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, somewhat poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in sandy recent alluvium or in calcareous silty or loamy recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant tree species are:

Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
 Peach-leaved Willow (*Salix amygdaloides*)

Sandbar Willow (*Salix exigua*)

73/73. Roxbury-Hord Subregion (Prairie Dog Creek, Solomon River-West, Smokey Hill River-West, Walnut Creek, Pawnee River) - Big Bluestem Prairie

Nearly level, silty soils on floodplains. The deep, well drained Roxbury soil is formed in silty, calcareous, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 20 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Hord soil is formed in silty, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 14 inches thick and moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 40-30
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 15-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 5-20
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM N-10

• Western Low Prairie

“A native lowland grassland community that occupies nearly level soils on floodplains along rivers, streams, and creeks. Soils are deep, poorly drained, and have formed in alluvium. these soils are nearly always saturated with water, or are seasonally inundated with surface water during the winter and/or spring seasons (Lauver, 1989)” Dominant plants include:

Prairie cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*)
 Sedges (*Carex* spp.)

• Western Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies nearly level, loamy, silty, and sandy soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, somewhat poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in sandy recent alluvium or in calcareous silty or loamy recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant tree species are:

Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
 Peach-leaved Willow (*Salix amygdaloides*)
 Sandbar Willow (*Salix exigua*)

74/74. Canadian-Platte Subregion (Arkansas River-Bend) - Big Bluestem Prairie

Nearly level, loamy and sandy soils on floodplains. The deep, well drained Canadian soil is formed in loamy, recent alluvium. It has a fine sandy loam surface layer about 15 inches thick and a moderately permeable fine sandy loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, somewhat poorly drained Platte soil is formed in sandy, recent alluvium. It has a loamy sand surface layer about 7 inches thick and a very rapidly permeable gravely coarse sand subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 25-30
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 15-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 15-10
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-N
 Eastern gamagrass (*Tripsacum dactyloides*) TRDA3 5-N
 Beaked panicum (*Panicum anceps*) PAAN 5-N
 Compass plant (*Silphium laciniatum*) SILA3 5-N
 Heath aster (*Aster ericoides*) ASER3 5-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 10-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS 5-N
 Prairies cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*) SPDE N-10

Trees included are:

Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
 Black Willow (*Salix nigra*)
 Sandbar Willow (*Salix exiqua*)

• Eastern Low Prairie

“A native lowland grassland community that occupies nearly level soils on floodplains along rivers, streams, and creeks. Soils are deep, poorly drained, and formed in alluvium. These soils are nearly always saturated with water, or are seasonally inundated with surface water during the winter and/or spring seasons. Short-term flooding of 1-3 days at depths less than two feet occurs periodically (2-12 times) through the year. The diversity of plant species is lower than in upland prairie communities. The distribution of this type is limited primarily to the floodplain areas of rivers, streams, and creeks (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

Cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*)
 Bulrushes (*Scirpus atrovirens*, *Scirpus* spp.)
 Sedges (*Carex* spp.)

Infrequent to common species include:

White wild indigo (*Baptisia lactea*)
 Panicked aster (*Aster simplex*)
 Sawtooth sunflower (*Helianthus grosserratus*)

- Shrub Swamp

“This community occupies inundated depressions, oxbow ponds, and sloughs of stream and river floodplains. Soils are deep and consist of peat or muck formed in alluvium. These soils are poorly drained; surface water is present for extended periods of the year. The vegetation is dominated in scattered clumps or dense thickets (50-100% cover) and tree coverage is less than 20 percent (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

Buttonbush (*Cephalanthus occidentalis*)
 Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

75/75. Detroit-Hord Subregion (Solomon River-East, Saline River, Smokey Hill

River-East) - Big Bluestem Prairie

Nearly level, silty soils on floodplains. The deep, moderately well drained Detroit soil is formed in silty, recent alluvium. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 14 inches thick and a thick and slowly permeable silty clay loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Hord soil is formed in silty, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 14 inches thick and moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-30
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 5-N
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 10-20
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) 10-5
 Blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*) BOGR2 N-5
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM N-10

Trees included are:

Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
 Black Willow (*Salix nigra*)
 Sandbar Willow (*Salix exiqua*)

- Eastern Low Prairie

“A native lowland grassland community that occupies nearly level soils on floodplains along rivers, streams, and creeks. Soils are deep, poorly drained, and formed in alluvium. These soils are nearly always saturated with water, or are seasonally inundated with surface water during the winter and/or spring seasons. Short-term flooding of 1-3 days at depths less than two feet occurs periodically (2-12 times) through

the year. The diversity of plant species is lower than in upland prairie communities. The distribution of this type is limited primarily to the floodplain areas of rivers, streams, and creeks (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

Cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*)
 Bulrushes (*Scirpus atrovirens*, *Scirpus* spp.)
 Sedges (*Carex* spp.)

Infrequent to common species include:

White wild indigo (*Baptisia lactea*)
 Panicked aster (*Aster simplex*)
 Sawtooth sunflower (*Helianthus grosserratus*)

• Shrub Swamp

“This community occupies inundated depressions, oxbow ponds, and sloughs of stream and river floodplains. Soils are deep and consist of peat or muck formed in alluvium. These soils are poorly drained; surface water is present for extended periods of the year. The vegetation is dominated in scattered clumps or dense thickets (50-100% cover) and tree coverage is less than 20 percent (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

Buttonbush (*Cephalanthus occidentalis*)
 Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

76/76. Verdigris-Brewer Subregion (Walnut River) - Big Bluestem Prairie

Nearly level, silty soils on floodplains. The deep, well drained Verdigris soil is formed in silty, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 20 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Brewer soil is formed in clayey, recent alluvium. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 15 inches thick and slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 30-25
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 10-15
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU 15-15
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smitthii*) AGSM N-5
 Canada wildrye (*Elymus canadensis*) ELCA4 N-5
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX N-5
 Eastern gamagrass (*Tripsacum dactyloides*) TRDA3 15-5

Beaked panicum (*Panicum anceps*) PAAN N-5
 Compass plant (*Silphium laciniatum*) SILA3 N-5
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC N-5
 Prairie cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*) SPPE 5-N

- Eastern Low Prairie

“A native lowland grassland community that occupies nearly level soils on floodplains along rivers, streams, and creeks. Soils are deep, poorly drained, and formed in alluvium. These soils are nearly always saturated with water, or are seasonally inundated with surface water during the winter and/or spring seasons. Short-term flooding of 1-3 days at depths less than two feet occurs periodically (2-12 times) through the year. The diversity of plant species is lower than in upland prairie communities. The distribution of this type is limited primarily to the floodplain areas of rivers, streams, and creeks (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

Cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*)
 Bulrushes (*Scirpus atrovirens*, *Scirpus* spp.)
 Sedges (*Carex* spp.)

Infrequent to common species include:

White wild indigo (*Baptisia lactea*)
 Panicked aster (*Aster simplex*)
 Sawtooth sunflower (*Helianthus grosserratus*)

- Shrub Swamp

“This community occupies inundated depressions, oxbow ponds, and sloughs of stream and river floodplains. Soils are deep and consist of peat or muck formed in alluvium. These soils are poorly drained; surface water is present for extended periods of the year. The vegetation is dominated in scattered clumps or dense thickets (50-100% cover) and tree coverage is less than 20 percent (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

Buttonbush (*Cephalanthus occidentalis*)
 Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

- Floodplain Woodland

“A mixed hardwood savanna community that occupies nearly level to gently sloping soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, somewhat poorly drained, and have formed silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” Dominant tree species include:

Bur oak (*Quercus macrocarpa*)
 Pecan (*Carya illinoensis*)
 Black willow (*Salix nigra*)
 Ash (*Fraxinus* spp.)

- Eastern Low Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies nearly level and undulating soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” Dominant tree species include:

Boxelder (*Acer negundo*)
 Hackberry (*Celtis occidentalis*)
 Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
 Sycamore (*Platanus occidentalis*)
 Pecan (*Carya illinoensis*)
 Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

- Eastern High Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies infrequently flooded and nearly level second (or high) bottoms and terraces along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).”

Dominant tree species include:

Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
 Green ash (*Fraxinus pennsylvanica*)
 Slippery elm (*Ulmus rubra*)
 American elm (*Ulmus americana*)

77/77. Eudora-Muir Subregion (Republican River, Kansas River) - Big Bluestem Prairie

Nearly level, silty soils on floodplains. The deep, well drained Eudora soil is formed in silty, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 14 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Muir soil is formed in silty, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 14 inches thick and moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 35-35

Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 5-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 15-10
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX N-5
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 5-10
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) SPAS N-5
 Prairie cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*) SPPE 10-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM N-5
 Kentucky bluegrass (*Poa pratensis*) POPR N-5
 Porcupinegrass (*Stipa spartea*) STSP2 N-5

- Eastern Low Prairie

“A native lowland grassland community that occupies nearly level soils on floodplains along rivers, streams, and creeks. Soils are deep, poorly drained, and formed in alluvium. These soils are nearly always saturated with water, or are seasonally inundated with surface water during the winter and/or spring seasons. Short-term flooding of 1-3 days at depths less than two feet occurs periodically (2-12 times) through the year. The diversity of plant species is lower than in upland prairie communities. The distribution of this type is limited primarily to the floodplain areas of rivers, streams, and creeks (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

Cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*)
 Bulrushes (*Scirpus atrovirens*, *Scirpus* spp.)
 Sedges (*Carex* spp)

Infrequent to common species include:

White wild indigo (*Baptisia lactea*)
 Panicked aster (*Aster simplex*)
 Sawtooth sunflower (*Helianthus grosserratus*)

- Shrub Swamp

“This community occupies inundated depressions, oxbow ponds, and sloughs of stream and river floodplains. Soils are deep and consist of peat or muck formed in alluvium. These soils are poorly drained; surface water is present for extended periods of the year. The vegetation is dominated in scattered clumps or dense thickets (50-100% cover) and tree coverage is less than 20 percent (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

Buttonbush (*Cephalanthus occidentalis*)
 Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

- Floodplain Woodland

“ A mixed hardwood savanna community that occupies nearly level to

gently sloping soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, somewhat poorly drained, and have formed silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” Dominant tree species include:

- Bur oak (*Quercus macrocarpa*)
- Pecan (*Carya illinoensis*)
- Black willow (*Salix nigra*)
- Ash (*Fraxinus* spp.)

- Eastern Low Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies nearly level and undulating soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” Dominant tree species include:

- Boxelder (*Acer negundo*)
- Hackberry (*Celtis occidentalis*)
- Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
- Sycamore (*Platanus occidentalis*)
- Pecan (*Carya illinoensis*)
- Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

- Eastern High Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies infrequently flooded and nearly level second (or high) bottoms and terraces along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).”

Dominant tree species include:

- Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
- Green ash (*Fraxinus pennsylvanica*)
- Slippery elm (*Ulmus rubra*)
- American elm (*Ulmus americana*)

78/78. Onawa-Haynie Subregion (Missouri River) - Big Bluestem Prairie

Nearly level, clayey and silty soils on floodplains. The deep, somewhat poorly drained Onawa soil is formed in clayey, recent alluvium. It has a silty clay loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and a slowly permeable silty clay subsoil and a silt loam substratum. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, moderately well drained Haynie soil is formed in silty, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 7 inches thick and moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 25-40
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 15-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 10-5
 Sedge (*Carex* sp.) CAREX 5-5
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 20-25
 Sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) BOCU N-5
 Tall dropseed (*Sporobolus asper*) 5-N
 Western wheatgrass (*Agropyron smithii*) AGSM 10-N
 Green needlegrass (*Stipa viridula*) STVI4 5-N

- Eastern Low Prairie

“A native lowland grassland community that occupies nearly level soils on floodplains along rivers, streams, and creeks. Soils are deep, poorly drained, and formed in alluvium. These soils are nearly always saturated with water, or are seasonally inundated with surface water during the winter and/or spring seasons. Short-term flooding of 1-3 days at depths less than two feet occurs periodically (2-12 times) through the year. The diversity of plant species is lower than in upland prairie communities. The distribution of this type is limited primarily to the floodplain areas of rivers, streams, and creeks (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

- Cordgrass (*Spartina pectinata*)
- Bulrushes (*Scirpus atrovirens*, *Scirpus* spp.)
- Sedges (*Carex* spp.)

Infrequent to common species include:

- White wild indigo (*Baptisia lactea*)
- Panicked aster (*Aster simplex*)
- Sawtooth sunflower (*Helianthus grosserratus*)

- Shrub Swamp

“This community occupies inundated depressions, oxbow ponds, and sloughs of stream and river floodplains. Soils are deep and consist of peat or muck formed in alluvium. These soils are poorly drained; surface water is present for extended periods of the year. The vegetation is dominated in scattered clumps or dense thickets (50-100% cover) and tree coverage is less than 20 percent (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

- Buttonbush (*Cephalanthus occidentalis*)
- Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

- Floodplain Woodland

“A mixed hardwood savanna community that occupies nearly level to gently sloping soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams.

Soils are deep, somewhat poorly drained, and have formed silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” Dominant tree species include:

- Bur oak (*Quercus macrocarpa*)
- Pecan (*Carya illinoensis*)
- Black willow (*Salix nigra*)
- Ash (*Fraxinus* spp.)

- Eastern Low Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies nearly level and undulating soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” Dominant tree species include:

- Boxelder (*Acer negundo*)
- Hackberry (*Celtis occidentalis*)
- Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
- Sycamore (*Platanus occidentalis*)
- Pecan (*Carya illinoensis*)
- Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

- Eastern High Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies infrequently flooded and nearly level second (or high) bottoms and terraces along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).”

Dominant tree species include:

- Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
- Green ash (*Fraxinus pennsylvanica*)
- Slippery elm (*Ulmus rubra*)
- American elm (*Ulmus americana*)

79/79. Osage-Verdigris Subregion (Verdigris River, Cottonwood River, Neosho River, Marais des Cygnes River) - Big Bluestem Prairie

Nearly level, clayey and silty soils on floodplains. The deep, poorly drained Osage soil is formed in clayey, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 15 inches thick and a very slowly permeable silty clay subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The deep, well drained Verdigris soil is formed in silty, recent alluvium. It has a silt loam surface layer about 20 inches thick and a moderately permeable silt loam subsoil. Slopes range from 0 to 3 percent. The predominant vegetation of this subregion, by % biomass, is:

Big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) ANGE 15-30
 Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) PAVI2 30-10
 Indiangrass (*Sorghastrum nutans*) SONU2 15-15
 Eastern gamagrass (*Tripsacum dactyloides*) TRDA3
 Little bluestem (*Andropogon scoparius*) SCSC 10-N
 Green needlegrass (*Stipa viridula*) STVI4
 Sunflower (*Helianthus* sp.) HELIA3 5-N

- Shrub Swamp

“This community occupies inundated depressions, oxbow ponds, and sloughs of stream and river floodplains. Soils are deep and consist of peat or muck formed in alluvium. These soils are poorly drained; surface water is present for extended periods of the year. The vegetation is dominated in scattered clumps or dense thickets (50-100% cover) and tree coverage is less than 20 percent (Lauver, 1989).” The dominant plants are:

- Buttonbush (*Cephalanthus occidentalis*)
- Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

- Floodplain Woodland

“A mixed hardwood savanna community that occupies nearly level to gently sloping soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, somewhat poorly drained, and have formed silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” Dominant tree species include:

- Bur oak (*Quercus macrocarpa*)
- Pecan (*Carya illinoensis*)
- Black willow (*Salix nigra*)
- Ash (*Fraxinus* spp.)

- Eastern Low Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies nearly level and undulating soils on floodplains along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).” Dominant tree species include:

- Boxelder (*Acer negundo*)
- Hackberry (*Celtis occidentalis*)
- Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
- Sycamore (*Platanus occidentalis*)
- Pecan (*Carya illinoensis*)
- Black willow (*Salix nigra*)

- Eastern High Floodplain Forest

“A mixed hardwood forest community that occupies infrequently flooded and nearly level second (or high) bottoms and terraces along major rivers and streams. Soils are deep, poorly drained to well drained, and have formed in silty and clayey recent alluvium (Lauver, 1989).”

Dominant tree species include:

Cottonwood (*Populus deltoides*)
Green ash (*Fraxinus pennsylvanica*)
Slippery elm (*Ulmus rubra*)
American elm (*Ulmus americana*)

* Floodplain Forest and Savanna (Kuchler, 1974).

REFERENCES CITED

Kuchler, A.W. 1974. A new vegetation map of Kansas. *Ecology*. 55:586-604

Lauver, Chris L. 1989. Preliminary classification of the natural communities of Kansas. Unpublished monograph. Kansas Natural Heritage Program. Kansas Biological Survey. The University of Kansas. April. 21 pp.

MAP 1: General Soil Map

MAP 2: Kansas Natural Regions Map

Kansas Pre-Settlement Grassland Ecosystems

MAP 3: Grassland Ecosystems Map